

English Material Development

“Applying CANVAS Online Learning Platform in Expressions of Invitation”

Nurhikmah Suci Pratiwi

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MODULE 1 : Speaking Prerequisites:

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Mark done
- **Example speaking in daily**
Mark done

MODULE 2 : Expression Of Invitation Prerequisites: MOD

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Quiz Prerequ

- **Module 1 and 2**
100 pts

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Introduction

Dear students,

Welcome to the **Online Learning for English Online Class**. I hope you are still healthy and well learning. You need to finish discussion, assignment, or quizzes before the due date. place be c will be locked and mark your presence place.

Please ask me questions if you need more explanation directly via inbox or my WhatsApp nu

All the best

Riezki Faradiena and Nurhikmah Suci Pratiwi

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Definition

Speaking is the skill that makes human beings different from and superior to the species of living animals. It is a linguistic skill. A child learns to speak through interaction with the people around him/her in his/her native language without effort and this skill is a natural one. But speaking in a second language requires conscious effort throughout the whole process.

There are a lot of functions of speaking in human lives every day. However, these functions can be categorized into three main types: Interaction, Transaction Performance.

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Example speaking in daily

Example I :

Taylor: Can I borrow your pen?

James: Oh sorry. I only have one pen i am using now

Taylor: Okay, then. Can I borrow your pencil?

James: Sure. Here it is

Taylor: Thanks, James

James: You are welcome

Example II :

Please watch the video below :

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Inviting, Accepting & Declining Invitat

Expression of Inviting

- Would you like to
- Could you come to...
- I'd very much like
- Would you care to
- I'll really happy if you come to....
- I'm sure that you won't be disappointed to come to....

Accepting an Invitation

- Thank you for inviting me.
- I would/will
- That would be very nice.
- I'd like to love to come.
- That's fine.
- Why not?

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Example of Dialog Invitation

Example I

Ludi Invites Maya to go to a Movie

Ludi : Hi, Maya. There will be a great film tonight. It's about vampire. Would you like to go to

Maya : Yes, I'd like to very much. When will you pick me up?

Ludi : I'll pick you at 7.00. Be ready, OK!

Maya : Alright.

Example II

Afif is very busy doing his homework. Sheila, his friend, asks him to come to her party.

Sheila : Heloo, this is Sheila. May I speak to Afif?

Afif : This is Afif speaking.

Sheila : Oh, hi Afif. I wonder if you'd like to come to my house right now.

We're having a great party.

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Preview

Module 1 and 2

Now, it's time to measure your understanding. I have seven questions that you must answer. You can't do this quiz before you read the materials in previous modules. Good Luck!

Quiz Type	Graded Quiz
Points	100
Assignment Group	Assignments
Shuffle Answers	Yes
Time Limit	No Time Limit
Multiple Attempts	Yes
Score to Keep	Highest
Attempts	3
View Responses	Always

Show Correct Answers After Last Attempt

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Module 1 and 2

This is a preview of the published version of the quiz

Started: Jan 5 at 6:37am

Quiz Instructions

Now, it's time to measure your understanding. I have seven questions that you must answer. You must complete this quiz before you read the materials in previous modules. Good Luck!

Question 1

20 pt

What is speaking? (You could pick more than one)

- An announcement on the board
- A message through speech
- Oral form
- Written form

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Question 2

10 pt

Why is speaking hard to apply when we learn new languages?

- Because the language is not their native language
- It is supposed to more effort by learners so people get messages.
- It is one of the skill should be learnt by students.G
- You usually interact by it.

Question 3

10 pt

One of the function of speaking is...

- Implementation
- Performance
- Symbolic

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Question 4

30 pt

There are three kinds of expressing an invitation. They are..

(You allow to choose more than one)

 Accepting All true Inviting Refusing

Question 5

10 pt

Dina wants to go to a market. She asks Rasti to accompany her. What should Dina say?

 That would be nice. Unfortunately, I can't go now.

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Question 5

10 pt

Dina wants to go to a market. She asks Rasti to accompany her. What should Dina say?

- That would be nice.
- Unfortunately, I can't go now.
- Thank you for inviting me.
- Would you like to go to a market with me?

Question 6

10 pt

Nasywa can't join to Mark's birthday party because her parents must come home late tonight. What will she say to Mark?

- Sure. Why not?
- I'll be happy if you come to my party.
- I'd like to, but my parents will come home late tonight.

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Help

Nasywa can't join to Mark's birthday party because her parents must come home late tonight. What will she say to Mark?

- Sure. Why not?
- I'll be happy if you come to my party.
- I'd like to, but my parents will come home late tonight.
- That's fine.

Question 7

10 pt

Chaca is excited that she receive an invitation card from Fara. She calls Rara and tells that she will come. What is possible statement by Chaca?

- Unfortunately, I can't join there.
- I'd love to come.
- Could you come to my house?
- I don't like attending a party